

A Comparative Study of Cystatin C and Creatinine as a Preliminary Marker of Nephropathy in Type 2 Diabetic Patients

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Abstract

Background: Type 2 diabetes disorder (T2DD) is one of the most common disorder in societies, and its causes are genetic and acquired. This disorder is characterized by an increase in the concentration of glucose in the blood. High concentrations of glucose in the blood for long periods lead to complications, the most important of which is diabetic nephropathy (DNP), which is characterized by the gradual loss of the kidney's filtration function.

Material and methods: The present study was designed based on collecting twenty patients with newly DNP (as first group) and twenty healthy individuals (as second group). The levels of HbA1c, Creatinine and Cystatin C of all study individuals were measured using Chromatographic assay method, Kinetic colorimetric method and Immunoturbidimetric assay techniques respectively.

Results: This study used the t-test statistical method to compare groups as well as sensitivity and specificity based on HbA1c, creatinine and Cystatin C biomarkers. The current study showed a higher the HbA1c percentage, creatinine level and Cystatin C level in the first group compared to the second group. On the other hand, the current study showed that Cystatin C has greater sensitivity and specificity than creatinine towards the DNP disease.

Conclusion: The current study concluded by stating the importance of the role of Cystatin C as an early indicator of DNP disease, as the current study proved that Cystatin C has greater sensitivity and specificity than creatinine towards DNP disease

Introduction

Type 2 diabetes disorder (T2DD) is a disorder that affects the body, causing the body's cells to not respond to the insulin hormone, and thus high blood glucose levels [1]. The causes of this disorder are commonly classified into two types: genetic and acquired, and effected population age more than 30 years. The symptoms and signs of T2DD are weight loss, fatigue, frequent thirst, difficulty healing wounds and etc. [2]. The presence of large amounts of glucose in the blood for long periods of time leads to other disease complications, the most famous of which is the

destruction of the renal nephron, which is called diabetic nephropathy (DNP). DNP can be defined as a gradual loss of kidney function due to the accumulation of large amounts of glucose in the blood (3). DNP is considered one of the most important causes of chronic kidney disease. The most important symptoms of infection DNP are loss of appetite, swelling of the feet, dry skin, nausea and others [4].

Cystatin C is known as an endogenous protein encoded by CST3 gene, It contains 120 amino acids and is found in most body tissues and fluids, the most important of which is kidney tissue [5]. Cystatin C plays important

More Information

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Keywords:

Type 2 diabetes disorder (T2DD), Diabetic nephropathy (DNP), Cystatin C, creatinine.

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roles in immune modulation, cell proliferation and inflammatory response, because it is a strong inhibitor of lytic proteases. The most important function and role of Cystatin C is as an early and important marker for predicting DNP, as it has high sensitivity and specificity for kidney diseases [6].

Creatinine is a nitrogenous compound produced through a non-enzymatic process from phosphocreatine or creatine directly, which plays an important role in the body's energy production, see figure 1. The amount of creatinine production in the

body is proportional to the body's muscle mass, and therefore the amount of creatinine in the body is almost constant and needs time for a noticeable change to occur [7]. Creatinine is considered a toxic substance in the body if it exceeds the normal limit, as it is disposed of through the kidneys to be excreted in the urine. Creatinine is considered one of the substances that are not reabsorbed by the renal tubules, and therefore it is used to diagnose kidney diseases [8].

Figure 1: Creatinine Production

The present study aims to compare between Cystatin C and creatinine in DNP patients, and to find out which is the best as a diagnostic marker.

Material and Methods

Our current study was designed based on the patient group and the healthy group and compared according to the determined biomarkers. Therefore, twenty individuals suffering with newly DNP (as first group) and twenty healthy individuals (as second group) were selected, their ages were 55-70 years of both genders, where the newly DNP samples were diagnosed based on the clinical characteristics , laboratory investigations

and clinical investigations approved in European Medicines Agency (EMA) 2024 Standards (9) . The study individuals were collected at Al-Yarmouk Teaching Hospital / Baghdad / Iraq from May - August 2024. Blood samples were drawn from all study individuals after take oral agreement from them and then divided into two sections:

**The first section was treated in a Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) tube to measure the percentage of hemoglobin A1C (HbA1C).*

***The second section was treated by centrifugation to obtain pure serum to measure the levels of Creatinine and Cystatin C.*

The all biomarkers details at this study show in below table:

Table 1: Biomarkers

Biomarker	Principle of assay	Kit ID	Company / country
HbA1C	Chromatographic assay	C1301a	Dx gen / Korea
Creatinine	Kinetic colorimetric method	B1123-3/0901	LINEAR CHEMICALS / Barcelona
Cystatin C	Immunoturbidimetric assay	KAI-074	KAMIYA BIOMEDICAL / USA

And this study was conducted after the 2013 Helsinki Declaration on the Ethics of Scientific Research. The two groups were compared according to the biomarkers HbA1c, Creatinine and Cystatin C, as well as according to the sensitivity and specificity between Creatinine and Cystatin C for the DNP patients group. All the above comparisons were made using a special statistical system called the T-test method, which is based on mean, standard deviation (SD), p-value sensitivity and specificity in SPSS program 2022, 26 version [10].

Results

In this study, a comparison was made between newly DNP group and healthy group according to Cystatin C, Creatinine and HbA1c using the statistical method called t-test which is based on mean ± SD and p-value. The results showed after comparing the two groups that there is an increase in the levels of Cystatin C, Creatinine and HbA1c in the newly DNP group compared to the healthy group. On the other hand, a comparison was made between the two groups according to the sensitivity and specificity of Cystatin C and Creatinine, and the study

showed that Cystatin C has a sensitivity and specificity for the DNP disease more than Creatinine. See table 2 and 3, and figure 2.

Figure 2: Explanation the Different Values between the Cystatin C and Creatinine Biomarkers in Newly DNP Group Depended on Sensitivity and Specificity

Table 2: Explanation the Different Values between Newly DNP Group and Healthy Group Depended on Cystatin C, Creatinine and HbA1c Biomarkers

Biomarker	Newly DNP group (mean ± SD)	Healthy group (mean ± SD)	p-value
Cystatin C (mg/L)	3.27 ± 1.27	0.91 ± 0.69	0.011*
Creatinine (mg/dl)	2.34 ± 0.61	1.07 ± 0.45	0.036*
HbA1C (%)	8.8 ± 1.17	6.1 ± 0.21	0.019*

Note: *significant value when the p-value < 0.05.

Table 3: Explanation the Different Values of Sensitivity and Specificity Percentage between Newly DNP Group and Healthy Group Depended on Cystatin C and Creatinine Biomarkers

Newly DNP group	Cystatin C	Creatinine	p-value
Sensitivity (%)	73.1	49.7	0.001*
Specificity (%)	61.5	35.2	0.001*
Healthy group	Cystatin C	Creatinine	p-value
Sensitivity (%)	15.5	21.0	>0.05
Specificity (%)	12.9	11.4	>0.05

Discussion

Diabetes mellitus is one of the most common and important disorder in societies around the world, and it has many causes, some of which are genetic and some

acquired [1]. One of the most important types of diabetes is T2DD, which has both causes. The presence of large amounts of glucose accumulated in the blood can cause other health problems and complications

besides diabetes, and the most common of these complications is DNP [4]. DNP is defined as the gradual loss of renal nephron function due to the filtration pressure on the kidney by accumulated glucose molecules. The onset of loss of nephron function is accompanied by several symptoms and complaints that appear in addition to changes in some markers of kidney function, the most important of these chemical makers are Cystatin C and Creatinine [11].

The results of our study showed the difference in the level of Cystatin C and Creatinine at the beginning of the disease DNP and therefore the samples were newly diagnosed with DNP. The results of the study showed an increase in the levels of Cystatin C and Creatinine for the newly DNP group compared to the healthy group. On the other hand, the study showed that Cystatin C has greater sensitivity and specificity than Creatinine towards the DNP.

Cystatin C is characterized by free glomerular filtration through the nephron, which makes it a unique marker for assessing the health of the renal nephron [12]. Also, an increase in the concentration of Cystatin C in human blood indicates a decrease in the glomerular filtration rate, due to kidney disease. Cystatin C production in the body is not affected by kidney condition, increased protein breakdown, or nutritional factors. Moreover, Cystatin production does not change with age or muscle mass like creatinine [13]. On the other hand, the level of creatinine is not affected until about half (50%) of the renal nephron tissue is damaged, while Cystatin C does not apply to this characteristic. Accordingly, the concentration of Cystatin C in the blood is more affected at the onset of kidney diseases, the most common of which is DNP. Therefore, the samples selected in this study were newly diagnosed disease samples with DNP [14].

The results of our current study are consistent with Hassan, M., Aboelnaga, M. M., et al (2021) who demonstrated an increase in the level of Cystatin C and creatinine in patients with DNP, and also consistent with Liao, X., Zhu, Y., et al. (2022) who demonstrated that Cystatin C has greater sensitivity and specificity than creatinine in patients with DNP [15,16].

Conclusion

Our current study concluded the importance of the role of Cystatin C and creatinine levels in the blood of newly DNP patients. The results of our current study showed that the level of Cystatin C in the blood is more sensitive and specific towards DNP disease in its early stages compared to the level of creatinine.

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Authors' Contribution

All authors contributed to data analysis, drafting and revising of the paper and agreed to be responsible for the all work aspects.

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest in this study.

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